

Fecal carriage of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in outpatients among Mongo communities, Chad

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Abstract

In recent years, the world has seen a surge in extended-spectrum β -lactamase-producing-bacteria. However, data on the dissemination of ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* in the community is not available in Chad. This study aims to determine the prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility pattern of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in fecal carriage from outpatients. From September 2017 to February 2018, 102 stools samples collected were sent at IRED. All stool samples were seeded onto Mac Conkey agar plates supplemented with cefotaxim (CTX, 2 μ g/mL), subjected to standard bacteriological method for isolation and characterization. Susceptibility to antibiotics was tested according to Kirby Bauer disk methods in respect to European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST, 2014). Out of the 102 samples investigated, 53 isolates were identified as *Escherichia coli* strains (84.9%) and *K. pneumoniae* (15.1%). Moreover, among the 53 strains, 33 (62.3%) belonged to extended spectrum β -lactamase producing (ESBL) group. The maximum resistance were observed with amoxicillin and clavulanic acid (82, 22%-87, 5%), nalidixic acid (93, 33%-100%), ciprofloxacin (71, 11%-75%), and gentamicin (80.00%-87.5%). *K. pneumoniae* resistance to fosfomycin was significant ($P = 0.011$) than *E. coli*. Mostly isolates tested were sensitive to imipenem. This result shows the high rate of ESBLs-producing isolates among outpatients in the community of Mongo. Surveillance of antimicrobial resistance needs to be implemented in Chad to tailor interventions targeted at stopping the dissemination of ESBL producing *Enterobacteriaceae*.

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Introduction

During the past few decades, ever-increasing use of antibiotic agents has led to selective pressure in favor of bacteria that have acquired resistance enzymes (Levy, 2004). Resistance to β -lactam antimicrobial drugs among gram-negative bacilli is mainly the result of extended-spectrum β -lactamase (ESBL), a major group of enzymes. ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* have been widely reported in many countries (Villegas *et al.*, 2011). These enzymes are typically plasmid-mediated and have the ability to hydrolyze all penicillin, third-generation cephalosporins and monobactams. They are not active against cephamycine or carbapeneme and are highly susceptible in vitro to inhibition by β -lactamase inhibitors, such as clavulanic acid (Thenmozhi *et al.*, 2014). The resistances to β -lactam antimicrobial drugs are often associated with resistances of other classes of antibiotics such as aminoglycosides, quinolones, sulfamides and others. The infections caused by these strains are very difficult to treat. *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* are two bacteria often detected in biological samples (Canton *et al.*, 2008). Dissemination of bacteria under human, capacity of these bacteria to produce ESBL has been shown among inpatients as well as among those in the community (Bou *et al.*, 2002).

The low hygiene measures are the first risk factors of bacterial transmission (Ali *et al.*, 2017). Studies from different countries report varying prevalence of ESBL-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* in the communities (Livermore *et al.*, 2012; Riaz *et al.*, 2012; Ahmed *et al.*, 2014).

In Chad, few studies on the prevalence of bacteria resistance to antibiotics have been reported in N'Djamena city by Yandai *et al.* (2014), Ndoutamia *et al.* (2015), Bessimbaye *et al.* (2015) and Linefiene *et al.* (2017). Data of antimicrobial resistant in rural communities is not available. The current study aims to determine the prevalence and antibiotic susceptibility

pattern of ESBL producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in fecal carriage from outpatients in the rural community of Chad.

Materials and methods

Samples collection

This prospective study was conducted at IRED in Chad, from September 2017 to February 2018. Stools samples given to outpatients presented at Mongo Hospital of Mongo for the parasitology diagnostic, 102 stools samples were collected in sterile disposable bottles and appropriately labeled at Mongo Hospital, province of Guera/Chad. These samples were taken with a swab and introduced into Cary Blair as transport medium. All samples collected were transported immediately at 4°C to the bacteriology laboratory of IRED in N'Djamena.

Bacteria isolation and identification

Stool samples were seeded onto MacConkey agar plates (Liofilchem, Italy) supplemented with cefotaxim (CTX, 2 μ g/mL) and incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours. All bacteria developing on MacConkey agar were suspected to be gram-negative bacilli and were sub-cultured on Mueller Hinton agar (Liofilchem, Italy) for the purification. Isolates were identified by their characteristic appearance, gram strains, mobility, biochemical reactions (lysine decarboxylase, carbohydrate fermentation, indole production, methyl red, voges proskauer, citrate) using 20E identification system (Biomerieux, Marcy l'Étoile, France).

Screening and confirming the presence of ESBL

Detection of ESBL production was screened on Muller-Hinton agar using a double-disc synergy test (DDST) according to the procedure of Jarlier *et al.*, (1988). The plates were inoculated with the strains as for standard disk diffusion test according to EUCAST (2014). Antibiotic disks containing cefotaxim (30 μ g), ceftazidim (30 μ g), cefepim (30 μ g), and aztreonam (30 μ g) disks were placed 30mm (center to center) from an amoxicillin/clavulanic acid disk prior to

incubation. After overnight incubation at 35-37°C, the production of ESBL by the tested organism was detected by the presence of characteristic distortions of the inhibition zones, indicative of clavulanate potentiation of the activity of the test drug. Negative double-disk tests were repeated with a disk spacing of 20mm (center to center).

Antibacterial susceptibility testing

Antibiotic susceptibility test was performed by Bauer *et al.*, (1966) disk diffusion method in respect to European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST, 2014). Pure culture of *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* was inoculated on Muller-Hinton agar plate (Liofilchem, Italy) with a depth of 4mm. Bio-Rad antibiotic disk used were: amoxicillin/clavulanic acid (20/10µg), cefoxitin (30µg), cefotaxim (30µg), ceftazidim (30µg), imipenem (10µg), aztreonam (30µg), gentamicin (10µg), amikacin (30µg), ciprofloxacin (5µg), ofloxacin (5µg) and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (1.25/23.75µg) and fosfomycine (10µg). Isolates were classified as susceptible or resistant according to EUCAST (2014). In the analyses intermediary resistant and resistant isolates were classified as non-

susceptible. *Escherichia coli* American Type Culture Collection (ATCC25922) were used as quality control strains.

Statistical analysis

All outcome data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 18.0 software and Microsoft Excel 2010. The differences between resistance patterns of germs strains were determined using Chi-square test of Pearson. All differences in which the probability of the null hypothesis was $p < 0.05$ were considered significant.

Results

Prevalence of *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*

In total, 102 patients had a fecal sample taken and analyzed. Out of these samples, 64 (62, 74%) bacteria were suspected to be gram-negative bacilli and all resistant to cefotaxim using for screening. Among these bacteria, 53 (51, 96%) *Enterobacteriaceae* were identified as *E. coli* (n = 45) and *K. pneumoniae* (n = 8).

This result indicated that the major group was *E. coli* (84.9%) than *K. pneumoniae* (15.1%). The prevalence was high in all age groups (table 1).

Table 1. Carriage prevalence of *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* according to age.

Age (years)	Patients (n=102)	<i>E. coli</i> (n=45)	<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (n=8)	Total (n=53)	Rate %
0 -14	23	9	1	10	43,48
15 - 29	12	2	0	2	16,67
30 - 44	32	15	3	18	56,25
45 - 59	23	11	3	14	60,87
60 and more	12	8	1	9	75,00
Total	102	45	8	53	51,96

Table 2. Antimicrobial susceptibility of *E. coli* and *K. Pneumoniae*.

Antibiotics	<i>E. coli</i> (n = 45)		<i>K. pneumoniae</i> (n = 8)		P value
	S (%)	R (%)	S (%)	R (%)	
AMC	8 (17,78)	37 (82,22)	1 (12,5)	7 (87,5)	0,714
IMP	44 (97,78)	1 (2,22)	7 (87,5)	1 (12,5)	0,160
FOS	42 (93,33)	3 (6,67)	5 (62,5)	3 (37,5)	0,011
CN	9 (20,00)	36 (80,00)	1 (12,5)	7 (87,5)	0,617
AK	24 (53,33)	21 (46,67)	5 (62,5)	3 (37,5)	0,631
NA	3 (6,67)	42 (93,33)	0 (0)	8 (100)	0,452
CIP	13 (28,89)	32 (71,11)	2 (25)	6 (75)	0,822
SXT	5 (11,11)	40 (88,89)	0 (0)	8 (100)	0,322

AMC: amoxicilline + acide clavulanique, IMP: Imipeneme, FOS: fosfomycine, CN: Gentamicine, AK: Amikacine, NA: Nalidixic acid, CIP: ciprofloxacin, SXT: Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole., S: sensitive, R: resistance.

Phenotype of ESBL detected

Out of the 53 isolates studied, 33 (62.3%) strains were confirmed ESBL producers (ESBL pos) by double-disk tests. However, 20 (37.7%) strains were tested negative and considered as ESBL no producers (ESBL neg). For the 33 ESBL-producing strains, 28 (45%) were *E. coli* strains and 5 (15.2%) were *K. pneumoniae* (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Carriage prevalence of ESBL- producing *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae*. Absolute numbers are presented within bars.

Antibiotic susceptibility

Result of Antimicrobial susceptibility showed the high resistance against amoxicillin + clavulanic acid (82.22%-87.5%), nalidixic acid (93, 33%-100%), trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (88.89%-100%), ciprofloxacin (71.11%-75%) and gentamicin (80.00% - 87.5%). A poor resistance was obtained with amikacin (46, 67%-37, 5%) and fosfomycine (6, 67%-37, 5%). Imipenem was very active on *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* tested. Two strains of *E. coli* and three of *K. pneumoniae* was resistant to fosfomycine. The resistance rates of *E. coli* compared to those of *K. pneumoniae* did not differ significantly for most antibiotics tested ($P > 0.05$), except for fosfomycine ($P = 0.011$) (Table 2).

Discussion

This study reveals the high rate of bacteria resistant to antibiotic used for infections treatment in Chad. Mostly *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* tested were resistant to third-generation cephalosporin. ESBL-producing-bacteria were detected as mechanism of resistance essentially. However, mostly bacteria tested were sensitive to imipenem.

This high rate observed with β -lactam antimicrobial may be due to several factors and practices. In Mongo region the laboratory for the culture and antimicrobial test is not implanted. All antibiotic used for the disease treatment are guided by clinical and etiological arguments. Many people can buy the antibiotics without medical prescriptions and on advice of street vendors.

According to Ndoutamia *et al.* (2017) many people in Chad believe that antibiotics can kill viruses, heal flu or reduce fever. The inappropriate consumption of antibiotics and empirical treatment of diseases constitute risks in selection of multidrug-resistant strains within the commensal flora. These bacteria may accept the plasmids and these plasmids can be transferred readily under stress to other species (Bagre *et al.*, 2015). In our findings, similar studies reports the rate ranged from 10 to 100% in West Africa (Ouedraogo *et al.*, 2017), 32.6% of children under 5 in Guinea-Bissau (Isendahl *et al.*, 2012), 10, 3% of hospitalized patients in Nigeria (Olowe *et al.*, 2010), 63% at the orphanage and 100% of staff members in Mali (Tande *et al.*, 2009). These different rates could be related to variations of health organization systems and differences between regions and targets.

In our study the rate was high in all age groups, also among the youngest where 43, 48% were carriers in the ages 0-14 years, and 75, 00% from 60 years and over. This indicates that colonization with ESBL-producing bacteria often occurs early in life and can increase with age in this population. For other antibiotics family other than β -lactam antimicrobial drugs, our findings found a maximum resistance to nalidixic acid and ciprofloxacin. In Chad, the ciprofloxacin and ofloxacin are often used for treatment of typhoid fever. Similar data about ciprofloxacin were presented by Ndoutamia *et al.*, (2015), Bessimbaye *et al.*, (2017).

According to Rodríguez-Baño *et al.*, (2004), the use of fluoroquinolones constitutes a risk factor for the acceptance and transfer of the resistance gene of ESBL-producing germs. For Guessennd *et al.* (2008), three genes implicated to quinolone resistance were: "QNR" genes, genes encoding N-acetyltransferase, ACC- (6')-IBCR and genes encoding the QepA efflux pump.

As for other antibiotics classes, the resistance to gentamicin is greater than 80%, but less with amikacin (62, 5%). This difference is due most likely to the difference of mechanism of resistance which may vary from one antibiotic to another. Similar study reported a rate from 73.3% to 94.7% in Madagascar (Andriatahina *et al.*, 2010). For our result, *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* were very resistant to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. This antibiotic was often used in empirical treatment of different syndromes diseases. This rate was similar to 95% reported in N'Djamena (Ndoutamia *et al.*, 2015), 98.6% in Sudan (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2013) and 91% in Nigeria (Iroma *et al.*, 2009). According to Guessennd *et al.*, (2008), the *qnr* A, B and S genes were present in *E. coli*. These genes were also responsible of plasmid resistance to trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, cefepim, cefoxitin and aminoglycosides. In contrast, fosfomycin was effective on most strains tested. The effectiveness of this molecule is linked with the fact that it is not available in peripheral environments. Its indication is much more restricted than quinolones, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole and aminoglycosides. This good bacterial sensitivity towards this antibiotic has also been reported by El Bouamri *et al.*, (2014) in Morocco.

Conclusion

This study revealed a high rate of ESBL-producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in Mongo. The use of drugs such as amoxicillin, trimetoprim/sulfamethoxazole and nalidixic acid does not seem appropriate for empirical treatment because of emergence. Several factors would be involved, self-

medication in the community and the empirical treatment to antibiotics. Thus, the risks of selection of multidrug-resistant strains within the commensal flora were therefore quite high and constituted a great threat to human and animal health. Further studies on the large scale on various clinical samples could help to learn more about the antibacterial drug resistance. At the molecular level, it is evident that much remains to be learnt about the control of expression of drug resistance genes.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests.

References

- Ahmed K, Raja I, Hussain I, Jan M, Nafees M, Jahan Z, Javeed M, Shah G, Latif A. 2014. Prevalence of *Escherichia coli* in suspected urinary tract infected patients and their sensitivity pattern against various *Escherichia coli* in suspected urinary tract infected patients and their sensitivity pattern against various antibiotics in Gilgit-Baltistan. Pakistan Journal of Zoology **46**, 1783-1788.
- Ali A, Sani O, Moumouni A, Zanguina J, Soussou A, Testa J, Halima BH. 2017. Antimicrobial status of salmonella meningitis in Niger. International Journal of Microbiology and Mycology **6(2)**, 1-6.
- Andriatahina T, Randrianirina F, Ratsima - Hariniana E, Talarmin A, Raobijaona H, Buisson Y, Richard V. 2010. High prevalence of fecal carriage of extended-spectrum β -lactamase-producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a pediatric unit in Madagascar. BMC Infectious disease **10**, 204.

- Bagré TS, Samandoulougou S, Traoré M, Illy D, Bsadjo G, Tchamba, Hadiza BI, Bouda SC, Traoré AS, Barro N.** 2015. Détection biologique des résidus d'antibiotiques dans le lait et produits laitiers de vache consommés à Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso. *Journal of Applied Biosciences* **87**, 8105-8112.
- Bauer AW, Kirby WM, Sherris JC, Turck M.** 1966. Antibiotic susceptibility testing by a standardized single disk method. *American Journal of Clinical Pathology* **45(4)**, 493-496.
- Bessimbaye N, Abdelsalam T, Guelmbaye N, Clement KH, Nicolas B.** 2015. Prevalence Multi-Resistant Bacteria in Hospital N'djamena, Chad. *Chemo Open Access* **4**, 4.
- Bou G, Cartelle M, Tomas M, Canle D, Molina F, Moure R, Eiros JM, Guerrero A.** 2002. Identification and broad dissemination of the CTX-M-14 β -lactamase-lactamase in different *Escherichia coli* strains in the northwest area of Spain. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* **40**, 4030-4036.
- Canton R, Novaisa A, Valverde A, Machado E, Peixe L, Baquero F, Coque TM.** 2008. Prevalence and spread of extended-spectrum β -lactamase-producing Enterobacteriaceae in Europe. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* **14(1)**, 144-153.
- El Bouamri MC, Arsalane L, Kamouni Y, Yahyaoui H, Bennouar N, Berraha M, Zouhair S.** 2014. Profil actuel de résistance aux antibiotiques des souches de *Escherichia coli* uropathogènes et conséquences thérapeutiques. *Progrès en Urologie* **24(16)**, 1058-1062.
- European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST).** 2014. Breakpoint tables for interpretation of MICs and zone diameters. Version 2.0, valid from 01-01, pp. 1-8.
- Guessennd N, Bremont S, Gbonon V, Kacou N, Douba E, Ekaza E, Lambert T, Dosso M, Courvalin P.** 2008. Résistance aux quinolones de type qnr chez les entérobactéries productrices de β -lactamases à spectre élargi à Abidjan en Côte d'Ivoire. *Pathologie Biologie* **8**, 439-446.
- Ibrahim ME, Bilal NE, Magzoub MA, Hamid ME.** 2013. Prevalence of Extended-spectrum β -Lactamases-producing *Escherichia coli* from Hospitals in Khartoum State, Sudan. *Oman Medical Journal* **28(2)**, 116-120.
- Iroha IR, Ezeifeke ES, Amadi ES, Umewurike CR.** 2009. Occurrence of Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase Producing Resistant *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in Clinical Isolates and Associated Risk Factors. *Research Journal of Biological Sciences* **4**, 588-592.
- Isendahl J, Turlej-Rogacka A, Manjuba C, Rodrigues A, Giske CG, Naucle P.** 2012. Fecal carriage of ESBL-producing *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* in children in Guinea-Bissau: a hospital-based cross-sectional study. *PLoS One* **7(12)**, e51981.
- Jarlier V, Nicolas, MH, Fournier G, Philippon A.** 1988. Extended broad-spectrum β -lactamases conferring transferable resistance to newer β -lactam agents in *Enterobacteriaceae*, Hospital prevalence and susceptibility patterns. *Reviews of Infectious Diseases* **10**, 867-878.
- Levy SB, Marshall B.** 2004. Antibacterial resistance worldwide: causes, challenges and responses. *Nature Médecine* **10**, 122-129.
- Linefiene L, Tankoano A, Fissou HY, Somda NS, Oumar O, Traore Y, Savadogo A.** 2017. Prévalence et sensibilité aux antibiotiques des souches de *Escherichia coli* diarrhéiques chez les enfants de moins de cinq ans au Tchad. *Revue de Microbiologie Industrielle Sanitaire et Environnementale* **11(1)**, 16-30.
- Livermore D.** 2012. Current Epidemiology and Growing Resistance of Gram-Negative Pathogens. *Korean Journal of Internal Medicine* **27**, 128-142.
- Ndoutamia G, Fissou HY, Bessimbaye N.** 2015. Antimicrobial Resistance in Extended Spectrum β -lactamases (ESBL) producing *Escherichia coli* from Human Urinary tract at the Mother and Child Hospital in Ndjamen, Chad. *Afr. J. Microbiol. Res.* **9(11)**, 776-780.

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- Ndoutamia G, Fissou HY, Nadjilem D, Gatsing D.** 2017. Perception, knowledge and use of antibiotic among communities in Chad. *African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology* **11(20)**, 260-265.
- Olowe OA, Grobbel M, Büchter B, Lübke-Becker A, Fruth A, Wieler LH.** 2010. Detection of bla (CTX-M-15) extended-spectrum beta-lactamase genes in *Escherichia coli* from hospital patients in Nigeria. *Int. J. Antimicrob. Agents* **35(2)**, 206-207.
- Ouédraogo AS, Jean Pierre H, Banyuls AL, Ouedraogo R, Godreuil S.** 2017. Facteurs favorisants et évaluation de la menace Emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance in West Africa: contributing factors and threat assessment. *Médecine et Santé Tropicales* **27**, 147-154.
- Riaz S, Faisal M, Hasnain S.** 2012. Prevalence and comparison of β -lactamase producing *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella spp* from clinical and environmental sources in Lahore, Pakistan. *Afr. J. Microbiol. Res.* **6**, 465-470.
- Rodríguez-Baño J, Navarro MD, Romero L, Martínez-Martínez L, Muniain MA, Perea EJ, Pérez-Cano R, Pascual A.** 2004. Epidemiology and clinical features of infections caused by extended-spectrum β -lactamase producing *Escherichia coli* in non hospitalised patients. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* **42(3)**, 1089-1094.
- Tande D, Jallot N, Bougoudogo F, Montagnon T, Gouriou S, Sizun J.** 2009. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing *Enterobacteriaceae* in a Malian orphanage. *Emerg. Infect. Dis.* **15(3)**, 472-474.
- Thenmozhi S, Moorthy K, Sureshkumar BT, Suresh M.** 2014. Antibiotic Resistance Mechanism of ESBL Producing Enterobacteriaceae in Clinical Field: A Review. *Int. J. Pure. App. Biosci* **2(3)**, 207-226.
- Villegas MV, Blanco MG, Sifuentes - Osornio J, Rossi F.** 2011. Increasing prevalence of extended-spectrum-beta-lactamase among Gram-negative bacilli in Latin America- 2008 update from the Study for Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance Trends (SMART). *Braz. J. Infect. Dis.* **15(1)**, 34-39.
- Yandai FH, Zongo C, Moussa AM, Bessimbaye N, Tapsoba F, Savadogo A, Barro N, Ndoutamia G, Traoré AS.** 2014. Prevalence and antimicrobial susceptibility of faecal carriage of Extended Spectrum β -lactamases (ESBL) producing *Escherichia coli* at the "Hôpital de la Mère et de L'Enfant" in N'Djamena, Chad. *Scientific Journal of Microbiology* **3(2)**, 25-31.